

Specific Characteristics of using Chinese Experience for Poverty Reduction in Uzbekistan

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Abstract. *This article describes the causes, main trends and ways of reducing poverty in Uzbekistan, as well as information on the effectiveness of using the experience of the Chinese state.*

Keywords: *Poverty problem, population income, educational opportunities, medical services, state infrastructure, quality drinking water supply, environmental ecology, population skills and potential, creation of new jobs.*

In Uzbekistan, the state strives to increase the effectiveness of social policy aimed at improving the quality of human capital and improving people's living standards. Nevertheless, the problem of poverty remains urgent for the country: 12-15 percent of the population is poor. This problem requires a solution.

Elimination of poverty in the country, first of all, economic development, sufficient number of jobs and access to them, increase in income of the population, opportunities for education, access to medical services, public infrastructure, supply of quality drinking water, environment depends on the environment. At the same time, the experience of countries that have successfully overcome poverty shows that it is impossible to eliminate poverty without simultaneous development of the social, economic and cultural spheres of human life.

In the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Oliy Majlis dated January 24, 2020, the fight against poverty is defined as a priority task. "Poverty reduction requires the implementation of a comprehensive economic and social policy, starting with the promotion of entrepreneurship, mobilizing the abilities and potential of the population, and creating new jobs." From this point of view, solving the issues of eliminating poverty, lifting the needy out of poverty, and creating effective mechanisms to prevent the increase in the number of low-income families is especially relevant today.

A long-term poverty reduction strategy is expected to be adopted, including comprehensive and targeted measures to reduce poverty across the country to the most remote areas.

At the moment, the government has started extensive research, and is working on the development of a national methodology for determining poverty, taking into account the best international experience. The international experience of poverty eradication is being actively studied. This work creates a methodological basis for a comprehensive assessment of the level of poverty in our country and for determining the criteria for inclusion of the population in the ranks of the needy. The calculation and approval of the minimum consumption basket and the minimum amount necessary for living provides the necessary basis for making further adjustments to the social security system, calculating benefits and making payments to the poor.

At the meeting chaired by the President on June 9 of this year, the current issues of ensuring the stability of the national economy, including future measures in the field of poverty reduction, were discussed. Taking into account the experience of China, the head of state gave orders to attach ministries and agencies to villages with a high level of poverty, create a system of providing assistance to the needy, and develop family business and estates.

A characteristic feature of the poor strata of the population is that it is several times more difficult to leave this group than to enter it. In most cases, the words "poverty" and "poverty trap" are used together. The poor not only do not benefit from the economic growth inherent in the country, but they also do not contribute to the development of society due to their limited access to social, educational and health opportunities.

The poor are also vulnerable to macroeconomic and natural shocks. For example, high inflation reduces the value of the poor savings of the poor, who typically have limited access to the banking system. In addition, since most of the poor are concentrated in rural areas and depend on agricultural activities, unexpected natural disasters can deprive them of their annual income.

Considering that Uzbekistan is actually developing only comprehensive approaches to poverty alleviation, it is important to study the international experience in fighting against poverty, taking into account the specific characteristics of Uzbekistan. or implementation of experience and solutions is extremely important. One of the clear examples in this regard is China's excellent results in getting rid of poverty.

The Chinese experience

Over the past 40 years, more than 800 million people have been lifted out of poverty in China, accounting for 70 percent of the world's total population lifted out of poverty. The poverty rate in China has decreased by 94 percent.

If in 1978, the number of poor people was 770 million people, which was 97.5% of the country's population, at the end of 2019, 5.5 million people live in poverty in China, which is 0.4% of the 1.4 billion population. organizes. Total population of China. During 1956-2018, per capita income increased by 36.8 times in real terms, and consumer spending by 28.5 times.

China's success in this regard is recognized by the international community. In particular, UN Secretary-General Antonio Guterres noted that China is a world record holder in poverty eradication in the last ten years. From 2013 to 2019, China lifted 82.4 million people out of poverty, and the proportion of people living below the national poverty line fell from 10.2 percent to 1.7 percent.

Between 2012 and 2018, China pushed more than 10 million people below the poverty line each year. China is expected to end extreme poverty in 2024, despite an economic downturn due to the impact of COVID-19. In recent decades, China has pursued an active policy of supporting agricultural producers, supporting internal labor migration from rural areas to urban areas, and paying special attention to poor border areas and ethnic minority areas, and improving the lives of women, children, the elderly, and the disabled.

In general, progress in China's fight against poverty began with agricultural reforms, partial privatization, and the abandonment of the planned approach in 1978-1985. China is a vivid example of how the development of agriculture and the elimination of rural poverty are carried out in an inseparable manner.

In the second half of the last century, China faced serious difficulties in providing its population with food; Implementation of land reform in villages, improvement of irrigation infrastructure led to increase in productivity, stable growth of agricultural production.

The following figures from the period of agricultural reform in China in 1978-1985 show. During this period, grain production per capita increased by 14%, cotton production by 73.9%, oil crops by almost 3 times, meat production by 87.8%, income per farmer by 3.6 times. . During 1949-2018, the area of irrigated land increased from 15.9 million hectares to 68.1 million hectares. China has become the world's largest exporter of many types of agricultural products.

From this point of view, after the adoption of the strategy for the development of agriculture until 2030 in Uzbekistan, systematic work on poverty reduction was started soon, its implementation will significantly change the current practice of agriculture and It is worth noting what and in what matters agricultural producers should be given more freedom.

In a country where agriculture accounts for 28% of the GDP and where the majority of the poor population is rural, agricultural reform and further development and poverty alleviation can be carried out separately. It is logical not to. In particular, conducting an experiment on the specialization of regions in the production of certain products in the Jizzakh region is one of the experiences of China, where a similar program is being implemented.

At the same time, China has actively solved housing problems, provided residents with quality drinking water, and increased access to medical services. Life expectancy in China has increased from 35 years in the 1950s to 77 years in 2018. In 2018, 95 percent of households were provided with clean drinking water. Social insurance system was created. As of March 2019, 941 million people were covered by basic insurance, with 1.3 billion people representing almost the entire population of China. One of the most important factors in China's success in reducing poverty is the nationwide nature of its efforts.

The private sector is actively participating in the fight against poverty in China, where more than 60,000 private enterprises have participated. One of the best examples of successful cooperation between the private sector and the countryside is Alibaba's Taobao Villages project, which enables villages to sell products through e-commerce, and it is worth noting the wide reach of the Chinese population with access to the Internet.

It all depends on the personnel

In both Uzbekistan and China, one of the most urgent problems in rural areas, especially in remote poor villages, is the acute shortage of personnel - effective managers and specialists.

The villages caught in the poverty trap will not be able to overcome it in the short term without attracting extensive knowledge and experience on the effective organization of economic life, taking into account the current social and technological development.

Limited opportunities for realizing human potential in remote poor areas leads to the fact that people with the necessary knowledge and skills do not go to these areas to engage in professional activities. From this point of view, China's practice of encouraging the flow of personnel, organizing training for rural residents, and sending and settling central government officials and party workers to poor villages has shown its results.

The clear vertical structure of the organization of the activities of the state apparatus for poverty reduction made it possible to coordinate the urgent issues of the population, increase the level and quality of the activities of local state authorities, and attract modern knowledge and skills. The gap between urban and rural areas in the level of education and the quality of provided educational services has decreased. Educational programs have been launched for the villagers to acquire specialization

Active conditions were created to attract the necessary personnel to poor villages. In particular, about 14 billion yuan was allocated for the construction of apartments for rural teachers in border areas and areas with difficult natural conditions, where 300,000 teachers were accommodated. Funds were allocated for subsidies to rural teachers - more than 600 1 million rural teachers received financial support.

The effectiveness of any measures or program strategies ultimately depends entirely on those who implement them. It is impossible to solve the problem of poverty in the country without attracting modern thinking personnel and effective managers with the necessary knowledge and skills to the poor villages..

Conclusion

In general, China's experience shows that the fight against poverty is comprehensive and targeted, and has determined the vector of socio-economic development of the country. At the same time, the task of reducing poverty can only be achieved through the parallel development of all aspects of human life, including meeting the minimum needs for food, drink, housing, and opportunities for education, health care, and professional services. can be solved by unlocking human potential by increasing.

Improving the well-being of the population in Uzbekistan is a strategically important and consistently resolved task. However, it was only later that the fight against poverty was consistently implemented in the state economic policy and formalized as a national goal. It was taken into account in the development and implementation of strategic programs and development plans of Uzbekistan. The specific tasks that Uzbekistan faces today in terms of increasing the standard of living of the population, reducing unemployment, encouraging the entrepreneurial activity of the population and increasing the income level have been successfully solved by China during the last decades, which in turn led to further development of the proposed reforms. China's economy has become the second largest in the world and has come close to eradicating poverty in the country.

Using China's experience will allow Uzbekistan to more successfully achieve its goals in this direction.

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